

GRAPHENE OXIDE FUNCTIONALIZATION WITH SILOXANES FOR ADVANCED COMPATIBILITY IN EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The improvement of the epoxy resin properties by the addition of functionalized graphene oxide (GO) depends on the compatibility of the organic polymer and inorganic reinforcing agent. The incorporation of GO functionalized with GPTS in epoxy matrix is expected to greatly increase the properties of the final composite by creating a compatible interface between the matrix and the GO.

Surface properties of the functionalized GO was proved by the deconvolution of high resolution C1 s XPS spectra, showing the attachment of GPTS molecules through ester linkage. In the same time, a quantification of the amount of GPTS which reacted with the carboxylic groups from GO was calculated from TGA degradation curves. The synthesized epoxy nanocomposites were analyzed by DSC, and the results revealed that the epoxy groups from the GPTS were involved in the cure reaction, leading to an increase of the cure enthalpy, which is a prove of the interface formation between GO-GPTS and epoxy matrix through a common network. Further investigation by SEM shows that functionalized GO are well dispersed in the polymer matrix.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer nanocomposites based on nanofillers like expanded graphite, carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers have been investigated in many studies due to their great thermal and mechanical properties [1]. Compared with conventional nanofillers, graphene has remarkable thermal, electrical and mechanical properties, while the high surface area is an advantage for great interface between reinforcing agent and epoxy matrix in high performance nanocomposites [1].

Graphene oxide is obtained from graphite through a process which involves two main steps: the first step corresponding to the graphite oxidation to obtain graphite oxide and the second step consist in the exfoliation of graphite oxide by sonication [3].

A new perspective in surface treatment and functionalization of GO takes into account to modify their surface with different agents in order to increase compatibility between polymer and GO when it is used as reinforcing agent. The oxygen containing groups from the GO surface like hydroxyl, carboxyl and epoxy, are suitable anchoring points for further functionalization. Graphene oxide and its derivates have created a new class of polymer nanocomposites, due their extraordinary thermo-physical properties and the ability to be compatibilized with in various polymer matrices[1].

Epoxy resins are one of the most important thermosetting polymer class used in a wide range of applications like: matrices for composites, paints and adhesive industry, impregnating varnishes, anticorrosive coatings, in electrical and electronics industry. All this applications are feasible due to their remarkable performance, processability and low cost [4]. In such an application approach, Bin

Yu and his team [5] dispersed MWCNT in silane and this solution was applied on carbon nanofibers. After that, the carbon nanofibers were compatibilized with epoxy resin to obtain nanocomposites. This nanocomposites showed improved interfacial bonding compared with the classical carbon fiber-reinforced resins.

Silanization offers GO the possibility to diversify their surface depending the type of organosilane attached to their surface [6]. The degree of GO surface functionalization through silanization is related to the functionality of the graphene specific surface area and silane concentration, but also the pH of the solution is important in order to obtain high yield [7]. Silanization of GO with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTS) was presented in a recent study dealing with the formation of covalent bonds between the epoxy groups from the GO surface and the amine groups of the APTS chain by a S_N2 mechanism [8]. The similar work of Yang et al.[1] performed a functionalization of GO with APTS developing an interest in the dispersion of functionalized GO in different polar or non-polar solvents. Wan et al. [4] functionalized graphene using APTS, showing improved dispersion and interfacial interaction between the functionalized graphene sheets and the epoxy matrix. This way increased tensile properties of epoxy/graphene nanocomposites were observed. In a recent study, the synthesis of reduced silanized graphene oxide and the reinforcement with this modified filler agent of a mixture epoxy-polyurethane is described. Thermogravimetric Analysis and Differential Scanning Calorimetry characterization showed that the thermal stability of the final composites was considerably increased [9].

The aim of this work was the functionalization reaction of GO with silanes having epoxy end groups and their use as reinforcing agent in polymeric systems like epoxy resins in order to obtain nanocomposites with improved properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. Materials

DGEBA type epoxy resin-(A506, EEW = 172-185 g/eq), (3-Glycidyloxypropyl)trimethoxysilane (GPTS, $\geq 98\%$), Hydrochloric acid, 37%, 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide, polymer-bound (EDC, Mw=10375 g/mol) and N-Hydroxysuccinimide (NHS, purum $\geq 97\%$) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. Sodium hydroxide was purchased from Chemreactiv (Romania). The chloroacetic acid (M=94.49 g/mol) was purchased from Merck and Jeffamine D230 was kindly supplied by Huntsman.

2.2. Method

GO functionalization

i) The first stage consists in the enhancement of the number of carboxyl groups at the GO surface. Thus, in a round bottom flask a 1 mg/mL suspension of laboratory synthesized GO [11] in water was prepared, then chloroacetic acid and NaOH were added, followed by ultrasonation for 3h. The mixture was neutralized with HCl solution 37%, then it was centrifuged and washed with distilled water until neutral pH. The black powder representing GO-COOH was dried under vacuum.

ii) The second stage is a carbodiimide coupling between GO-COOH and GPTS. At this point, GO-COOH was suspended in water under sonication for 2h, then a solution of EDC in PBS buffer (pH=5.5) was added and the sonication was continued for another 30 minutes. The NHS coupling agent was introduced and the pH was reduced to 1.5 with HCl solution 5%, then GPTS was added and sonicated for 30 minutes. The resulted suspension was filtrated and washed with distilled water until neutral pH. The GO-GPTS was dried under vacuum for 24h.

Epoxy nanocomposites synthesis

Calculated amounts of unmodified and GPTS functionalized GO (1 wt.%) were mixed with a polymer matrix consisting in a mixture of diglycidylether of bisphenol A (A506) and fluorinated epoxy resin (REF) synthesized by our team [12]. The two types of epoxy resin were mixed in a 2:1 wt. ratio. The mixture was then sonicated using a tip sonicator for 2 h having 60% amplitude at room temperature. Then the D230 hardener was added to the mixture and vigorously stirred for 2 min. The mixture was then cast into a mold and cured at 50°C for 3 h followed by 1 h postcuring process at 100 °C.

2.3 Materials characterization

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) curves were registered on a Q500 TA Instruments equipment, under nitrogen atmosphere using a heating rate of 10°C/min from room temperature to 800°C.

The surface structures for different types of GO were studied by X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) using a K-Alpha instrument from Thermo Scientific, with a monochromatic Al K_α source (1486.6 eV), at a bass pressure of 2×10⁻⁹ mbar. Charging effects were compensated by a flood gun and binding energies were calibrated by placing the C 1s peak at 284.8 eV as internal standard. The pass energy for the survey spectra was 200 eV and 20 eV for high resolution. Deconvolutions of the C 1s peaks were performed after Shirley's inelastic background subtraction and were normalized for the measured transmission function of the spectrometer.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) curves were recorded on a Netzsch DSC 204 F1 Phoenix equipment. The sample was heated from RT to 300 °C using a heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen (20 mL/min flow rate).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was done on a Quanta Inspect F (FEI) instrument, with field emission electron gun, 1.2 nm resolution and X-ray energy dispersive spectrometer having an accelerating voltage of 30 kV. For a better contrast, the samples were first fractured in liquid nitrogen and covered with a thin gold layer.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compatibility between epoxy matrix and the surface of the reinforcing agent has a great influence on the thermo-physical properties of the designed nanocomposites, due to enhanced dispersity which will lead to good transfer of the mechanical stress within these materials. TGA was used to quantify the amount of GPTS which was attached through functionalization (Fig. 1) in comparison with the laboratory synthesized GO and the carboxylated ones. It was noticed that the initial decomposition temperature was lowered by the GPTS attachment, meaning that the newly formed structures are more sensitive than the initial oxygenated groups. The GO-GPTS samples show a four step degradation mechanism, compared with the degradation curves of GO and GO-COOH which presents only three steps. The supplementary degradation step between 300-450°C can be ascribed to the breakage of GPTS molecules attached to the GO surface.

Figure 1. TGA curves for the GO and functionalized GO.

Another important parameter which can be calculated from the TGA curves is the mass loss of the samples (Table 1). The increase of the mass loss with almost 10% was attributed to the attachment of GPTS molecules to the GO surface through ester linkage as it was later observed in the deconvolution of high resolution XPS analysis (Table 2).

Sample	$T_{d3\%}$		Mass loss 25÷900°C	
GO	73	[°C]	60.4	[%]
GO-COOH	69	[°C]	65.1	[%]
GO-GPTS	53	[°C]	69.7	[%]

Table 1. Thermal properties of the GO and functionalized GO

The surface elemental analysis by XPS survey spectra showed the appearance of the Si 2p species after functionalization, as well as C 1s and O 1s compared with the GO and GO-COOH samples where only C 1s and O 1s were noticed. Even if the amount of Si 2p was 2.2% related to the total amount of atoms taken into account, these data are completing our TGA studies.

Figure 2 High resolution XPS spectra for C1s from GO-COOH (a) and GO-GPTS (b)

Sample	C At. %	O At. %	Si At. %
GO-COOH	79.7	20.3	-
GO-GPTS	71.2	26.6	2.2

Table 2 Surface properties of the GO and functionalized GO

The study of the cure reaction between epoxy matrix and the polyetheramine was realized by DSC analysis. The epoxy reaction enthalpy was calculated from the exothermic peak area (Table 3) of the DSC curves and it shows an increased value 1% GO-GPTS was added. The difference between the two types of sample can be attributed to a higher amount of epoxy groups which reacts with the curing agent, thus covalent bridges of ester on one side of the functionalized GO and C-N bonds on the other side are connecting the matrix with the reinforcing agent. In the same time, a slight shift of the maximum curing temperature (with about 2°C) was noticed, which is caused by the steric hindrance exerted by the GO sheets in the nanocomposite system.

Sample	Area	T_{max}
A506+50%REF+D230	301.1 [J/g]	114.7 [°C]
A506+50%REF+1%GO-GPTS+D230	363.2 [J/g]	116.7 [°C]

Table 3 DSC data for the cure reaction of the epoxy matrix and for the nanocomposites

The morphology of the epoxy nanocomposites fracture surface was observed in the SEM images from figure 3. The difference between the cured matrix and the nanocomposites consist in a higher roughness which is caused by an advanced compatibility between the components which lead

to a difficult extraction of GO during fracture. It can be observed also that the fracture edges are well defined in the nanocomposites samples due to a efficient dispersion of GO sheets which are orienting the fracture mechanism.

Figure 3 SEM images for the epoxy matrix (A) and the GO-GPTS reinforced nanocomposites (B)

9 CONCLUSIONS

Surface modification of GO with epoxy silane was accomplished through an EDC-NHS coupling mechanism adopted from peptide chemistry. The surface composition was monitored using XPS and the presence of GPTS molecules was confirmed. A rough quantification from the high resolution C 1s XPS spectra was correlated with the calculations from the TGA mass loss. Epoxy nanocomposites reinforced with the new nanomaterials were obtained with good dispersion, the supplementary curing sites given by the GPTS functional groups from the GO surface were translated in higher cure reaction enthalpy.

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